

Kinetics of Haloaminometric Reactions. Mechanism of Oxidation of Thiocyanate Ion by Chloramine-B and Bromamine-B in Acid Medium

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Manuscript received 28 August 1985, revised 19 March 1986, accepted 7 June 1986

Kinetics of oxidation of thiocyanate ions by chloramine-B (CAB) and bromamine-B (BAB), sources of Cl^+ and Br^+ species, have been studied in presence of perchloric acid at 283 K. The rate of reaction was first order in $[\text{NCS}^-]_0$ with both the oxidants. Pseudo-first order rate constants slightly decreased with the increase in $[\text{BAB}]_0$. The rate was independent of $[\text{H}^+]$ with CAB, but had slight dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ with BAB. Variation of ionic strength of the medium or addition of the reaction products had no effect on the rate with both CAB and BAB. However, the decrease of dielectric constant of the medium decreased the rate with both the oxidants. Thermodynamic parameters have been computed in both the cases. Mechanistic schemes in conformity with the observed kinetics have been proposed and the corresponding rate laws derived. In some cases rate constants for the rate controlling steps have been calculated.

THE chemistry of aromatic *N*-haloamines has evinced considerable interest due to their diverse behaviour¹. They are sources of halonium cations, hypohalite species and *N*-anions which act both as bases and nucleophiles. Due to their greater stability they are used as disinfectant and antiseptic in preference to hypohalites. Although these oxidants have been extensively used as analytical reagents²⁻⁹, there is scant information about the mechanistic investigations⁹⁻¹⁶. Further, the toluene analogues⁹⁻¹⁵ are more commonly used than benzene analogues¹⁶. As a part of our mechanistic investigations of haloaminometric reactions in general and thiocyanate reactions in particular, we report herein the results of kinetics of oxidations of thiocyanate ion by chloramine-B (CAB) and bromamine-B (BAB) in perchloric acid medium.

The thiocyanate reactions are of interest due to their medicinal and biological importance. They also find applications in analytical chemistry. There are very few reports on the kinetics of oxidation of thiocyanate ion. The oxidants so far used are H_2O_2 ¹⁷, aqueous iodine¹⁸, Cr^{VI} ^{19a}, V^{VI} ^{19b}, Bi^{V} ²⁰, chloramine-T^{11,12}, bromamine-T^{13a} and iodamine-T^{13b}.

Experimental

Potassium thiocyanate (Merck, analytical grade) was dried at 150° and its purity checked by standard methods²¹. An aqueous stock solution (~0.1 mol dm⁻³) of the substrate was prepared. Chloramine-B was prepared by the partial chlorination of benzenesulphonamide (BSA)²² in 4 *M* NaOH for 1 h at 70°.

Bromamine-B was obtained by the partial debromination of dibromamine-B⁹. The purity of the oxidants was checked by estimating the amount of active halogen present in them and by recording their spectra. Aqueous stock solutions of the oxidants (0.1 mol dm⁻³) were prepared, standardised and stored in dark coloured bottles. All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic runs were made under pseudo-first order conditions with $[\text{NCS}^-] \gg [\text{CAB}]_0$ or $[\text{BAB}]_0$ (at least by 5–10 times) in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes whose outer surfaces were coated black to eliminate photochemical effects. The reactions were initiated by the quick addition of appropriate quantities of CAB or BAB solution, thermally equilibrated at a desired temperature, to a mixture of measured amounts of thiocyanate solution, perchloric acid and water (to keep the total volume constant), pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for two half-lives by iodometric estimation of unreacted CAB or BAB in the reaction mixture at regular time intervals. The pseudo-first order rate constants obtained by the method of least-squares were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. Preliminary investigations showed that ionic strength of the medium had no effect on the rate.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometries of the $\text{NCS}^- - \text{CAB}$ and $\text{NCS}^- - \text{BAB}$ reactions were determined under $[\text{NCS}^-] \gg [\text{oxidant}]$ conditions at different $[\text{H}^+]$ (0.001–0.10 mol dm⁻³) by thermally equilibrating various ratios of $[\text{NCS}^-]$ to $[\text{CAB}]$ or $[\text{BAB}]$ at 283 K for 24 h. The products were identified as sulphate and cyanate by standard methods²³⁻²⁵. Benzenesulphonamide (BSA), the

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reduced product of CAB or BAB, was detected by thin layer chromatography²⁶. A mixture of petroleum ether, chloroform and n-butanol (2 : 2 : 1, v/v) was the solvent with iodine as the detecting reagent ($R_f=0.88$). Further, the sulphate was quantitatively estimated by gravimetric method²¹. The observed stoichiometry can be represented as

where, $\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2$.

Results

The kinetics of oxidation of thiocyanate ion by CAB and BAB, sources of Cl^+ and Br^+ species, under pseudo-first order conditions were investigated at several initial concentrations of NCS^- , CAB or BAB and H^+ in perchloric acid medium at 283 K (Tables 1 and 2).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[\text{OX}]$, $[\text{NCS}^-]$ AND $[\text{H}^+]$ ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF THIOCYANATE ION BY CHLORAMINE-B (CAB) AND BROMAMINE-B (BAB) IN ACID MEDIUM AT 283 K

$10^4[\text{OX}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4[\text{NCS}^-]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3[\text{H}^+]$ mol dm ⁻³	10^4k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)	
			CAB	BAB
2.0	2.0	0.1	17.1	—
2.0	2.0	0.5	17.1	15.3
2.0	2.0	1.0	17.1	17.1
2.0	2.0	2.5	17.1	19.0
2.0	2.0	5.0	17.1	19.7
2.0	2.0	7.5	17.1	21.0
2.0	2.0	10.0	17.1	23.0
2.0	0.8	1.0	6.9	6.1
2.0	1.0	1.0	8.8	8.1
2.0	2.0	1.0	17.1	17.1
2.0	4.0	1.0	38.4	30.7
2.0	5.0	1.0	46.1	46.3
2.0	7.5	1.0	67.0	—
2.0	8.0	1.0	—	72.5
2.0	10.0	1.0	88.6	96.0
1.0	2.0	1.0	17.1	20.7
1.5	2.0	1.0	17.1	19.2
2.0	2.0	1.0	17.1	17.1
3.0	2.0	1.0	17.1	15.4
4.0	2.0	1.0	17.1	14.1
6.0	2.0	1.0	17.1	12.8
8.0	2.0	1.0	17.1	11.1

Oxidation with chloramine-B : At constant $[\text{H}^+]$ with several fold excess of $[\text{NCS}^-]$, plots of $\log ([\text{CAB}]_0/[\text{CAB}])$ vs time were linear. Pseudo-first

order rate constants were insensitive to the variation of $[\text{CAB}]_0$ (Table 1) and to $[\text{H}^+]$ (0.001–0.1 mol dm⁻³) at constant $[\text{CAB}]_0$ and $[\text{NCS}^-]_0$. But the rate increased with the increase in $[\text{NCS}^-]_0$ and a plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{NCS}^-]$ was linear with unit slope, showing first order in $[\text{NCS}^-]_0$.

Oxidation with bromamine-B : At constant $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{NCS}^-]$, $\log [\text{BAB}]_0/[\text{BAB}]$ vs time plots were linear and pseudo-first order rate constants decreased with the increase in initial concentrations of BAB. But the rate increased with the increase in $[\text{NCS}^-]_0$ at constant $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{BAB}]_0$. The log–log plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{NCS}^-]_0$ was linear with unit slope, indicating first order dependence of rate on $[\text{NCS}^-]_0$. At constant $[\text{BAB}]_0$ and $[\text{NCS}^-]_0$, the rate increased slightly with the increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ (0.005–0.1 mol dm⁻³) and a plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{H}^+]$ was linear with a slope of 0.14. Thus the rate had little dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$.

Addition of the reaction products BSA and Cl^- or Br^- had no effect on the rate (Table 2) in both the oxidations. Decrease of dielectric constant of the medium by changing the solvent composition decreased the rate with both the oxidants. The $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ plots were linear with negative slopes (Fig. 1). The thermodynamic parameters have

Fig. 1. (O) $\log k_{\text{obs}} > < 1/D$; $10^3[\text{H}^+] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³, $10^4[\text{CAB}]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm⁻³ and $10^4[\text{ONS}^-] = 2.0$ mol dm⁻³; (X) plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}} > < 1/D$; $10^4[\text{BAB}]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm⁻³, $10^3[\text{H}^+] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³ and $10^4[\text{ONS}^-] = 2.0$ mol dm⁻³; temp. = 283 K.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF THE MEDIUM AND ADDING REACTION PRODUCTS ON THE RATE OF REACTION AT 283 K*

D	10^4k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)		$10^3[\text{BSA}]$ mol dm ⁻³	10^4k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)		10^4k_{obs} s ⁻¹	BAB $10^4[\text{Br}^-]$ mol dm ⁻³	10^4k_{obs} s ⁻¹
	CAB	BAB		CAB	BAB			
83.7	17.1	17.1	0.0	17.1	17.1	0.0	0.0	17.1
81.6	16.1	16.5	0.1	17.1	17.1	0.1	1.0	17.1
78.9	13.8	13.7	1.0	17.1	17.1	1.0	2.0	17.1
74.1	11.7	6.1	10.0	17.1	17.1	10.0	5.0	17.1
64.4	8.3	3.5	—	—	—	—	10.0	17.1

* $10^4[\text{ONS}^-]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm⁻³; $10^3[\text{H}^+] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³; $10^4[\text{CAB}]_0$ or $[\text{BAB}]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm⁻³.

been computed in both the cases by measuring rates at different temperatures (Table 3).

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF THIOCYANATE ION BY CHLORAMINE-B (CAB) AND BROMAMINE-B (BAB)

Parameters	CAB	BAB
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	50.74	62.23
log A	6.60	8.01
$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	48.89	59.88
$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-21.59	-21.78
$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	54.50	66.04

Discussion

Chloramine-B and bromamine-B¹⁶, like chloramine-T^{1,9} are moderately strong electrolytes in aqueous solutions,

where, X=Cl or Br. RNCl^- and RNBr^- pick up protons in the acid medium to give conjugate acids RNHCl and RNHBr , respectively,

which in turn undergo disproportionation to RNCl_2 and RNBr_2 ,

and hydrolyse to HOCl and HOBr ,

In strong acid solutions, RNHCl and RNHBr may give RNH_2Cl^+ and RNH_2Br^+ , respectively,

which in turn undergo hydrolysis to give H_2OCl^+ and H_2OBr^+ ,

Therefore, the probable oxidising species in the acid solutions of CAB and BAB are RNHX and HOX , and possibly RNH_2X^+ and H_2OX^+ (X=Cl or Br). In the acid medium, NCS^- picks up a proton to give hydrothiocyanic acid,

Mechanism of oxidation :

With chloramine-B : The observed kinetics for the oxidation of NCS^- by CAB in the acid medium can be accounted through Scheme 1

Scheme 1

and rate law (9),

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAB}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{CAB}][\text{HNCS}] \quad (9)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = -\frac{d \ln [\text{CAB}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{HNCS}] \quad (10)$$

Plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{HNCS}]$ was linear with straight line passing through the origin (with slope = $k_1 = 0.89 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2), in conformity with the rate law (10), and hence the reaction Scheme 1.

Fig. 2. (O) Plot of $k_{\text{obs}} > < [\text{NCS}^-]$; $10^3[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $10^4[\text{CAB}]_0 = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (X) plot of $k_{\text{obs}} > < [\text{NCS}^-]$; $10^3[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $10^4[\text{BAB}]_0 = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; temp = 283 K.

With bromamine-B : The observed results with BAB can be explained through Scheme 2

Scheme 2

and rate law (11),

$$-\frac{d[\text{BAB}]}{dt} = \frac{K_3 k_4 [\text{RNHBr}]_0 [\text{HNCS}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{1 + K_3 [\text{RNHBr}]_0 + K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{or } k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_3 k_4 [\text{HNCS}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{1 + K_3 [\text{RNHBr}]_0 + K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k_4 [\text{HNCS}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \left[\frac{1 + K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{K_3} + [\text{RNHBr}]_0 \right] \quad (13)$$

At constant $[H^+]_0$ and $[HNCS]_0$, a plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[BAB]_0$ was linear with an intercept on the ordinate (Fig. 3) in agreement with rate law (13).

Fig. 3. (O) Plot of $k_{obs} >> [H^+]$; $10^4[BAB]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm^{-3} and $10^2[ONS^-]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm^{-3} , (X) plot of $1/k_{obs} >> [BAB]_0$; $10^2[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3} and $10^4[ONS^-]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm^{-3} , temp. = 283 K.

The observed slight dependence of rate on $[H^+]$ may be due to a small fraction of the reaction going through an alternate path (Scheme 3).

The corresponding rate law is

$$k_{obs} = K_6 k_7 [HNCS] [H^+] \quad (14)$$

The combined rate law (15) accounts for the observed kinetics with bromamine-B,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_6 k_7 [HNCS] [H_2O]}{1 + K_6 [RNHBr]_0 + K_6 [H_2O] + K_6 k_7 [HNCS] [H^+]} \quad (15)$$

For $[HNCS]$ and $[H^+]$ variations, the rate law (15) becomes

$$k_{obs} = [HNCS] [k + K_6 k_7 [H^+]] \quad (16)$$

Where,

$$k = \frac{K_6 k_7 [H_2O]}{1 + K_6 [H_2O]} \text{ as } \{1 + K_6 [H_2O]\} \gg K_6 [RNHBr]_0$$

The linear plot of k_{obs} vs $[HNCS]$ (Fig. 2), passing through the origin and the plot of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ with an intercept on the ordinate (Fig. 3) are in conformity with rate law (16).

Although an alternate Scheme 4, may be proposed to explain the observed results with BAB,

the rate law (17) obtained by applying steady state approximations,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_9 k_{10} [H^+] [HNCS]}{1 + K_9 [H^+] + K_9 [BAB]_0} \quad (17)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{k_{10} [HNCS]} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{K_9 [H^+]} + \frac{[BAB]_0}{[H^+]} \right\} \quad (18)$$

predicts a linearity between $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[H^+]$. But the plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[H^+]$ (Fig. 4) was not linear, ruling out Scheme 4, for explaining observed kinetics with bromamine-B.

Fig. 4. Plot of $1/k_{obs} >> 1/[H^+]$; $10^4[BAB]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm^{-3} and $10^2[ONS^-]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm^{-3} , temp. = 283 K.

The observed non-influence of ionic strength of the medium and products, benzenesulphonamide and Cl^- or Br^- , on the rate are in agreement with mechanistic Schemes proposed with both the oxidants.

The observed decrease of rate with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium with both chloramine-B and bromamine-B are in conformity with Amis theory^{27,28}. For the limiting case of zero angle of approach between two dipoles or an ion-dipole systems, Amis has shown that a plot

of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ (Fig. 1) gives a straight line with a negative slope for a reaction between two dipoles or a dipole and a negative ion. This concept agrees with the present observations and suggested reaction schemes, which involve mostly dipoles in the rate controlling steps in both cases.

It is evident from the comparison of kinetic data with CAB and BAB that they are similar except a little dependence of rate on $[H^+]$ with BAB. Even the rate constants are same at standard run concentrations (Table 1), the indifferent behaviour of $[H^+]$ on the rate with respect to CAB and BAB may be due to the difference in the electronegativities of chlorine and bromine atoms. Since the electronegativities of chlorine and nitrogen atoms are equal, monochloramine-B (RNHCl) may be relatively neutral when compared to monobromamine-B (RNHBr), where the electronegativity of N-atom is higher than that of Br-atom. The difference in electronegativities between N and Br atoms makes the N-atom more negative in BAB. As a result, H^+ ion approaches the negative end more easily and releases Br^+ readily from the oxidant, thus increasing the rate of reaction and showing the rate dependence on $[H^+]$ with BAB. This phenomenon is in conformity with the proposed mechanisms and provide additional support to the latter.

Acknowledgement

This work has been partly supported by a Research Grant, from U.G.C., New Delhi.

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